

IMPROVING READING LITERACY SKILLS IN FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL
TEACHERS

Kayumova Shoxsanam To'lqin qizi

Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor,

Email: shoxsanamkayumova0523@gmail.com

Shahlo Naraliyeva

Zumabek Tashenev is the director of the Department of International Relations of the University of the Republic of Kazakhstan,

Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor,

Email: shahlonaraliyevna84@gmail.com

Musurmonkulov Muhammad Urol o'gli

Independent researcher

Email: musurmankulovamhammad0523@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11116018>

Abstract. Today, the development of methodological training of teachers is the most urgent. This article describes the theoretical and practical importance of developing the reading literacy of future primary school teachers.

Key words: reading literacy, modern trends, international assessment programs, Collaboration and Feedback, Interactivity, Purposeful Selection of Resources, Technology Integration, Accessibility.

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ НАВЫКОВ ЧИТАТЕЛЬНОЙ ГРАМОТНОСТИ У
БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ НАЧАЛЬНЫХ ШКОЛ

Аннотация. Сегодня развитие методической подготовки учителей является наиболее актуальным. В данной статье описывается теоретическая и практическая значимость развития читательской грамотности будущих учителей начальных классов.

Ключевые слова: читательская грамотность, современные тенденции, международные программы оценки, Сотрудничество и обратная связь, Интерактивность, Целенаправленный отбор ресурсов, Интеграция технологий, Доступность.

In the realm of primary education, the significance of proficient reading literacy among teachers cannot be overstated. The development of reading skills in future primary school educators is a pivotal undertaking, essential for fostering a culture of lifelong learning and

excellence in pedagogy. This article delves into the importance, challenges, and strategies involved in cultivating robust reading literacy skills in prospective primary school teachers.

Importance of Reading Literacy for Future Teachers

The ability to read proficiently is not only a fundamental academic skill but also a cornerstone of effective teaching. Future primary school teachers must embody exemplary reading skills to navigate the diverse curriculum demands, comprehend educational research, and inspire young minds through storytelling and literature. Moreover, proficient readers are better equipped to model literacy behaviors and impart essential reading strategies to their students.

Challenges in Developing Reading Literacy Skills

Despite its paramount importance, nurturing reading literacy skills in future educators encounters several challenges. Time constraints within teacher training programs, competing priorities, and variable levels of prior literacy exposure among aspiring teachers present hurdles in comprehensive skill development. Additionally, addressing individual learning needs and fostering a genuine passion for reading amidst technological distractions pose significant challenges.

Strategies for Enhancing Reading Literacy

To effectively enhance reading literacy skills among future primary school teachers, a multifaceted approach is indispensable:

Integrated Curriculum: Infuse reading-focused coursework and activities within teacher training programs, emphasizing comprehension strategies, critical analysis, and exposure to diverse literary genres.

Professional Development: Facilitate ongoing workshops and seminars to sharpen reading skills, explore emerging research in literacy education, and promote best practices in teaching reading.

Modeling and Mentoring: Encourage mentorship programs where experienced educators model effective reading strategies and provide constructive feedback to aspiring teachers.

Collaborative Learning Communities: Foster communities of practice where future teachers engage in book clubs, peer reviews, and collaborative reading projects to enhance reading proficiency collectively.

Technology Integration: Leverage digital tools and educational apps to promote interactive reading experiences, access to e-libraries, and multimedia resources that complement traditional literacy instruction.

Cultivating a Reading Culture: Instill a love for reading by celebrating literature through author visits, literary events, and school-wide reading initiatives, encouraging future teachers to be reading role models.

In the digital age, modern technologies offer unprecedented opportunities to enhance reading literacy among learners of all ages. This article explores how innovative digital tools and platforms can be leveraged effectively to improve reading skills, foster engagement, and promote a lifelong love for reading.

The Role of Modern Technologies in Reading Literacy

Modern technologies, ranging from interactive apps to e-readers and online libraries, play a pivotal role in transforming traditional reading practices. These tools offer personalized learning experiences, accessibility features, and interactive elements that cater to diverse learning styles and preferences. By integrating technology into literacy education, educators can bridge gaps, enhance comprehension, and inspire a new generation of avid readers.

Digital Tools for Reading Enhancement

E-Readers and Digital Libraries: E-readers like Kindle and digital libraries such as Project Gutenberg provide instant access to a vast collection of books, enabling readers to explore diverse genres and authors conveniently.

Interactive Reading Apps: Educational apps like Epic! and ReadingIQ offer interactive stories, comprehension quizzes, and audio features that enhance engagement and comprehension skills among young readers.

Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR): AR and VR applications bring stories to life, immersing readers in interactive narratives and virtual worlds that stimulate imagination and deepen comprehension.

Text-to-Speech and Voice Recognition: Tools like Voice Dream Reader and Google Docs Voice Typing assist struggling readers and individuals with disabilities by offering text-to-speech and voice recognition capabilities.

Gamification of Reading: Platforms like Reading Eggs and Lexia Core5 use gamified elements to motivate readers, track progress, and reinforce literacy skills through playful learning experiences.

Benefits of Technology-Enhanced Reading Literacy

The integration of modern technologies into literacy education yields numerous benefits:

Accessibility: Digital tools make reading accessible to learners with disabilities and those in remote areas with limited access to physical books.

Personalization: Technology enables personalized learning pathways tailored to individual reading levels and preferences.

Engagement and Motivation: Interactive features, gamification, and multimedia elements enhance engagement and sustain motivation for reading.

Data-Driven Insights: Digital platforms provide real-time data on reading habits and performance, enabling educators to make informed instructional decisions.

Challenges and Considerations

While modern technologies offer transformative potential in literacy education, challenges such as digital divide, privacy concerns, and maintaining a balanced approach between screen time and traditional reading practices must be addressed thoughtfully.

Conclusion

In conclusion, leveraging modern technologies is instrumental in improving reading literacy across diverse populations and age groups. By embracing digital tools, educators can create immersive, engaging, and inclusive reading experiences that empower learners and cultivate a lifelong passion for reading. The future of literacy education lies at the intersection of innovative technology and pedagogical best practices, enabling every learner to unlock the transformative power of reading in the digital era. In sum up, the development of reading literacy skills among future primary school teachers is instrumental in shaping the quality of education and fostering a lifelong passion for learning among young students. By acknowledging the challenges and implementing targeted strategies, educational institutions can empower aspiring teachers to become adept readers and advocates of literacy. Investing in the reading proficiency of future educators is not merely a pedagogical necessity but a transformative investment in the future of education.

REFERENCES

1. Qayumova, S. (2022). БЎЛАЖАК БОСИЛАНҒИЧ СИНОФ ЎҚИТУВСЧИЛАРИНИ TIMSS ХАЛҚАРО БАҲОЛАШ ДАСТУРИ АСОСИДА МЕТОДИК ТАЙЁРГАРЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА МУЛТИМЕДИЯ ВОСИТАЛАРИНИНГ ЎРНИ. *Science and innovation*, 1(B4), 159-162.
2. Shohsanam, K. (2023). THEORETICAL IMPORTANCE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE. *Science and innovation*, 2(Special Issue 3), 159-162.
3. Kayumova, S. T. qizi, Sharipov, S. R., Abdullayev, K. A. ugli, & Nurmatov, I. S. (2023). THE THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF IMPROVING STUDENTS' READING

• ZAMONAVIY ILM-FAN VA TA'LIM ISTIQBOLLARI •
ILMIY-AMALIY KONFERENSIYASI

- PROFICIENCY BASED ON MODERN TRENDS. *RESEARCH AND EDUCATION*, 2(12), 57–61.
4. To'liqin qizi Kayumova, S., Sharipov, S. R., ugli Abdullayev, K. A., & Nurmatov, I. S. (2023). THE THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF IMPROVING STUDENTS'READING PROFICIENCY BASED ON MODERN TRENDS. *RESEARCH AND EDUCATION*, 2(12), 57-61.
 5. Kayumova, S. T. K. (2022). DIFFERENCES BETWEEN PISA AND TIMSS INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT PROGRAM. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(NUU Conference 2), 753-757.
 6. Sh. Kayumova (2023). DIDACTIC PRINCIPLES FOR DEVELOPING NATIVE LANGUAGE AND READING LITERACY OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS. *Science and innovation*, 2 (B9), 57-60. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8348958
 7. Sh. Kayumova (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' READING LITERACY THROUGH TRIZ PEDAGOGY. *Science and innovation*, 2 (B10), 157-160. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8433398
 8. Qayumova, S. (2022). БЎЛАЖАК БОСШЛАНҒИЧ СИНФ ЎҚИТУВСЧИЛАРИНИ TIMSS ХАЛҚАРО БАҲОЛАШ ДАСТУРИ АСОСИДА МЕТОДИК ТАЙЁРГАРЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА МУЛТИМЕДИЯ ВОСИТАЛАРИНИНГ ЎРНИ. *Science and innovation*, 1(B4), 159-162.
 9. 9.Urol o'gli, M. M. (2024, April). ENHANCING READING LITERACY THROUGH TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION. In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 2, No. 4, pp. 229-233).
 10. To'liqin qizi Kayumova, S., ugli Abdullayev, K. A., ugli Khujamurodov, O. M., & Markabayev, F. T. (2024). THE THEORETICAL IMPORTANCE OF THE STEAM PROGRAM IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION. *RESEARCH AND EDUCATION*, 3(1), 29-33.
 11. Qizi, Q. S. T. L. (2024). ENHANCING THE READING LITERACY OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH MODERN TRENDS. *Science and innovation*, 3(Special Issue 18), 190-193.
 12. 9. Shahriddinovna, K. S. (2023). Didactic Features Of Development Of Nature Perception Skills Of Primary School Students. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 19, 183-187.

13. Shahridinovna, K. S. (2023). INTRODUCING CHILDREN OF PRIMARY SCHOOL AGE WITH THE WORLD. *American Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(06), 09-14.
14. Shahridinovna K. S. Didactic Features Of Development Of Nature Perception Skills Of Primary School Students //Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching. – 2023. – T. 19. – C. 183-187.
15. Shahridinovna K. S. INTRODUCING CHILDREN OF PRIMARY SCHOOL AGE WITH THE WORLD //American Journal of Applied Science and Technology. – 2023. – T. 3. – №. 06. – C. 09-14.
16. Karimova, S. (2022). THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF" NATURAL SCIENCES" IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF UNDERSTANDING OF NATURE IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS. *Science and innovation*, 1(B6), 214-218.
17. Karimova S. THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF" NATURAL SCIENCES" IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF UNDERSTANDING OF NATURE IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS //Science and innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. B6. – C. 214-218.
18. Karimova S. CHARACTERISTICS OF NATURAL TEACHING METHODOLOGY //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 737-740.
19. Karimova, S., & Ashurova, M. (2023). TYPES OF EDUCATION. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(8), 161–163. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/22537>
20. Mamatova, X., Karimova, S., & Turg'unboyeva, M. (2023). EDUCATION IS UPBRINGING, KNOWLEDGE IS SALVATION. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(8), 164–166. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/22538>
21. Mamatova, . H., Karimova, S., & Mamayusupova, . Z. (2023). PEDAGOGICAL ANALYSIS IN THE WORKS OF ALISHER NAVOI. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 5–8. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/23865>
22. Karimova S., Habibullayeva S. THE ESSENCE OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN PEDAGOGY //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 1. – C. 40-44.
23. Karimova Sevara Shaxriddin Qizi. (2023). FORMATION OF NATURE AWARENESS SKILLS OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *International Scientific and Current*

Research Conferences, 1(01), 43–45. Retrieved from
<https://www.orientalpublication.com/index.php/iscrc/article/view/1105>

24. Mamatova H., Karimova S., Mamayusupova Z. PEDAGOGICAL ANALYSIS IN THE WORKS OF ALISHER NAVOI //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 9. – C. 5-8.
25. Sevara, K., & Maftuna, S. (2024, February). BOSHLANG 'ICH SINFLARDA ONA TILI DARSLARIGA QO'YILGAN ZAMONAVIY TALABLARNING XUSUSIYATI VA AHAMIYAT. In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 65-67).
26. Sevara, K., & Mahliyo, X. (2024, February). BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLARDA O'QUVCHILARIDA MATEMATIK QOBILIYATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA QO'LLANILADIGAN METODLAR. In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 68-70).

MODERN SCIENCE
& RESEARCH